

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS THROUGH MEDIA LITERACY

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Abstract: This thesis talks about the development of creative thinking of future elementary school teachers based on the basics of using media and increasing their capacity to develop their creative abilities, and introducing them to educational technologies to enrich their worldview.

Key words: media literacy, student, creative skill, ability, educational system, quality, technology.

Introduction:

One of the most urgent issues today is the development of creativity skills of primary school teachers. Therefore, one of the efforts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the reform of the education sector is the activity of pedagogues in accordance with the requirements of the times, having deep knowledge, pedagogical skills, skills, qualifications and culture to educate a well-developed person in all aspects demands that they be. This automatically brought the concept of "creativity" to the science of pedagogy, which studies the laws of education and upbringing.

Creativity is creativity (lat. Create - create, creative - creative) - the creative ability that characterizes the individual's readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. Therefore, today there is a social order to develop the creativity of teaching staff in general education schools, and it is necessary to conduct scientific pedagogical research in this regard. However, the scientific-theoretical, scientific-pedagogical aspects of the issue of creativity have not been investigated as a special object of scientific research. Today's modern continuous education system requires a creative approach. In particular, primary education is one of the types of education that leaves a deep mark on the life of every child, and at this stage of education, pedagogues have a great responsibility. That is, the creative activity of primary school teachers still requires special study.

That is why it is said to develop creative thinking based on introducing innovative educational technologies to increase the intellectual potential of elementary school teachers and enrich their worldview. One of the important issues of today is the consistent development of competence-based qualities and creative abilities of primary school teachers through the use of innovative

teaching technologies in educational practice. There are a number of factors that influence the development of creative abilities of primary school teachers, as well as the stages of development of creative abilities.

That is why primary school teachers should always work on themselves and develop their creativity. The priority task of general education is to form not only the intellect of students, but also the spiritual and emotional sphere, creative approach to work, which is a condition for the efficiency of future professional activity and social adjustment. The task of a modern teacher is to teach children self-awareness, self-control, self-discipline, to teach them to make the right choice, to think creatively is to teach. Therefore, primary school teachers should always work tirelessly on themselves. Therefore, today the development of creative abilities becomes a vital issue.

The purpose of our work is to determine and justify the pedagogical conditions and tools for the development of creative activity of primary school teachers. Theoretically, it is necessary to develop and practice the ability of elementary school teachers to be creative, free improvisation, to find new parallels in ordinary things and events, to create an atmosphere of calmness, benevolence, and to solve any problems in the classroom.

- ❖ analysis of literature on the development of creative abilities of primary school teachers in reading classes;
- ❖ analysis of psychological-pedagogical conditions for the development of knowledge activity of elementary school teachers in artistic processing in technology lessons;
- ❖ development of practical skills for the technology of artistic processing of paper in technology lessons for elementary school teachers;
- ❖ to develop a methodology for conducting technology lessons based on the methods of developing students' creative abilities;
- ❖ verification of the developed methodology in practice.

Currently, the study of creativity of elementary school students is of particular importance, so many studies are being carried out. The conducted studies showed that there is a mutual relationship between the creativity and thinking characteristics of primary school students. Applying a differential approach to elementary school students has a positive effect on the activation of their creativity. In addition to this, primary school teachers themselves can educate students in the same spirit only if they are creative. In the process of education, the following processes increase students' creativity.

- Ensuring the awareness and effectiveness of reading, connecting the content of the text with the experiences and impressions of the students.
- Work on a lot of vocabulary in the implementation of conscious reading.
- Teaching and memorizing from poems, quick sayings, riddles, songs, proverbs, wise words,
- When teaching to read, it creates a free opportunity to fill in words and sentences, compose sentences, and think independently.
- Concepts such as the teacher listening to each student, not interrupting the student even if he knows that they are thinking incorrectly, and listening even if there is a mistake, are examples.
- Creativity can be developed with the help of pictures.

We have to tell students to imagine "an incredible solution to a problem." This encourages students in the process of creation to feel confident in their own creation, encourages them to be creative.

Summary:

In conclusion, it can be seen from the above results that when primary school teachers themselves have creative abilities, they can educate students in this spirit. In addition to this, in the organization of each of the lessons, one should be able to organize the lessons in a creative way that is convenient for children and encourages them to constantly search for themselves.

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